

1 **Optimizing Hyaluronan-Based Lubricants for Treating Thoracolumbar Fascia Pathologies:**
2 **Insights from Tribological and Pharmacokinetic Studies**

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11
12 **Abstract**

13 In a world where the incidence of non-specific lower back pain (LBP) is steadily increasing,
14 researchers are still searching for effective solutions for patients. Hyaluronic acid (HA)
15 viscosupplementation is commonly used to restore lubrication in osteoarthritis (OA) and other
16 medical applications, but its rapid metabolism limits efficacy. This study evaluates whether an
17 HA derivative can replace native HA for the treatment of non-specific LBP while maintaining
18 or enhancing its frictional properties and improving *in vivo* stability. Six HA-based lubricants,
19 both native and derivatized, were tested in a tribological rabbit fascia model and a new synthetic
20 model. Reduced HA derivative showed better tribological properties, non-toxicity and longer
21 *in vivo* residence time compared to native HA, as demonstrated in pharmacokinetic studies in
22 rabbits. The 316 kDa HA and reduced HA exhibited the most stable tribological properties,
23 which were influenced by their molecular weight and concentration. These findings suggest
24 that both native and reduced HA are promising viscosupplements for intrafascial injection in
25 the treatment of LBP, with reduced HA potentially enhancing effectiveness through a prolonged
26 effect.

29 **Key words**

30 Lower back pain, hyaluronic acid, fascia, friction, viscosupplementation

31

32 **1. Introduction**

33 In recent years, there has been a significant increase in cases of lower back pain (LBP) among
34 individuals [1; 2]. The treatment for LBP can be financially burdensome and prolonged, often
35 without accurately diagnosing the underlying cause. As a result, many individuals may
36 experience work incapacity [1]. Research suggests that one possible cause of LBP could be the
37 thoracolumbar fascia (TLF), which undergoes pathological changes [3; 4; 5]. Healthy fascia
38 typically consists of two or three layers of connective tissue that glide smoothly and are
39 lubricated by hyaluronic acid (HA) [6]. However, an unhealthy lifestyle and overuse syndromes
40 can lead to structural changes in the fascia.

41

42 Such changes in the fascia can include densification and fibrosis, which are distinct pathological
43 alterations. The two alterations often occur simultaneously. Fibrosis refers to a pathological
44 change in the fibrous component of the fascia, characterized by the random accumulation of
45 collagen fibers. This type of change is challenging to modify manually during rehabilitation.
46 On the other hand, densification is a change in the viscosity of the loose connective tissue within
47 the fascia, resulting from the more viscous HA [7; 8; 9]. This causes patients with chronic LBP
48 to exhibit reduced gliding of the TLF [5]. Furthermore, it has been proposed that heightened
49 muscle exertion elevates the molecular weight (*MW*) of HA, consequently increasing its
50 viscosity [10; 11], while the increase in viscosity of HA is also associated with immobilization
51 [12]. This elevation in viscosity may impede normal muscle movement within loose connective
52 tissue. Analogous to its function in joint and synovial fluid, heightened HA production
53 represents an initial effort by the fascia to enhance its mobility. At elevated concentrations, HA

54 behaves similarly to a non-Newtonian fluid, exhibiting increased viscosity as the HA chains
55 entangle, thereby contributing to the solution's hydrodynamic characteristics [6]. The
56 heightened viscosity of HA, coupled with the sparsity of connective tissue due to pathological
57 alterations within and upon the fascia, reduces the sliding between the collagen fiber layers of
58 the deep fascia, consequently resulting, again, in a sensation of stiffness in the patient's back.

59

60 Viscosupplementation with HA is widely used to restore lubrication and improve the gliding of
61 connective tissues in osteoarthritis (OA), as well as to reduce friction and enhance comfort
62 between contact lenses and the eye [13]. Intrafascial injections of HA, a promising therapeutic
63 approach recently introduced by our group, could similarly restore the reduced gliding ability
64 of the fascia by reducing friction between its layers [14]. Despite the long-standing use and
65 proven clinical efficacy of HA injections for conditions such as OA and as skin fillers, the rapid
66 metabolism of native HA in the body limits its duration of action. Therefore, this study aims to
67 determine if native HA used in viscosupplementation for treating non-specific LBP can be
68 effectively replaced with a derivative that maintains or even enhances its frictional properties
69 while offering improved *in vivo* stability. We rigorously tested six HA-based lubricants, in both
70 native and derivatized forms on tribological model of rabbit fascia introduced in [15].
71 Simultaneously, a new synthetic model was introduced to verify lubricants' influence on fascia
72 friction. The most promising derivative based on tribological testing, reduced HA [16], exhibits
73 nontoxic properties and biodegradability comparable to native HA, as demonstrated in a
74 pharmacokinetic study involving rabbits.

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79 **2. Materials and methods**

80 **2.1 Lubricants**

81 Native HA (101, 316 and 610 kDa) and HA derivatives (reduced HA (HA RED and lauroyl
82 modified HA (HA-C12)) provided by Contipro a.s. (Czech Republic) were dissolved in PBS
83 and sterilized by filtration. Concentrations and viscosity of tested solutions are summarized in
84 Tab 1 Lubricants used for tribological tests. Structures of HA derivatives are displayed in S.Fig. 1.

85

86

Tab 1 Lubricants used for tribological tests

Designation	Molecular weight (kDa)	Degree of substitution	Concentration (mg/ml)	Viscosity (mPa.s, 37 °C)
610 kDa HA	610	-	20	1191
316 kDa HA	316	-	20	202
101 kDa HA	101	-	20	27
316 kDa HA (lower conc.)	316	-	10	59
HA-RED	275	18 %	20	122
HA-C12	318	9.1%	3	37

87

88 For the pharmacokinetics study, solution of ¹³C-labelled 316 kDa HA and solution of HA-RED
89 were prepared in normal saline (0.9% NaCl) at a concentration of 10 mg/ml. Labelling of HA
90 with the nonradioactive isotope ¹³C was used to distinguish the administered HA from
91 endogenous HA [17]. After sterilization by filtration, they were additionally autoclaved.
92 Apyrogenicity of the solutions was then verified using a portable endotoxin testing system
93 (Endosafe® nexgenPTS™ testing system, Charles River Laboratories, USA) and only
94 apyrogenic samples (endotoxin levels < 0.1 IU/ml) were used for study.

95

96

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98 **2.2 Tribological setup**

99 Bruker UMT TriboLab (Bruker, Billerica, MA, USA) was used to measure friction and
100 lubrication properties of test samples. The tribometer sensor recorded the normal and friction
101 force, from which the value of the friction coefficient was calculated as a function of time. The
102 static pin was loaded by 2N normal force. The plate moved with a 1Hz frequency of reciprocal
103 linear motion and 12mm track length. The same amount of lubricant and test temperature were
104 kept for each test (2 ml of lubricant, 37 °C). Two types of experiments were conducted based
105 on change in the test time. The short-term 300s tests were repeated 5-times. The long-term
106 3000s tests were tested 3-times. Experimental conditions were chosen based on physiological
107 conditions, therapy, and limitations of the test facility. For more information, refer to the
108 Materials and Methods section in the previous publication [15].

109
110 The experimental apparatus, in pin-on-plate configuration, consisted of a pot and pin part. The
111 pin has a convex surface with a 50mm radius on which the polydimethylsiloxane (PDMS) with
112 a 1mm thickness is embedded. The fascia is stretched over the surface of the pin and PDMS,
113 which is attached with jaws screwed into the pin. The pot is divided into two main parts. The
114 lower part provides attachment to the tribometer, heating cartridges, and assembly of jaws to
115 hold the sample. In the bottom part, PDMS is inserted and over it, fascia is prestressed by the
116 jaws. The lubricants examined in this study were laid on elastomer PDMS of 10 ShA stiffness
117 simulating underlying muscle. Sliding friction tests were carried out for prepared
118 thoracolumbar rabbit fascia and SynDaver™ synthetic fibrous fascia tissue.

119

120 **2.3 Preparation of samples of rabbit TLF**

121 Sexually mature New Zealand white rabbit with a body weight of at least 3 kg, was used for
122 preparation of TLF for tribological testing. The rabbits were first sedated by subcutaneous

123 administration of medetomidine (0.3 mg/kg; Domitor inj., Orion Corporation, Espoo, Finland)
124 and then induced into general anaesthesia by intramuscular administration of ketamine (25
125 mg/kg; Narkamon inj., Bioveta, Ivanovice na Hane, Czech Republic). Subsequently, the
126 animals were stunned with a captive bolt gun and then exsanguinated by transecting the carotid
127 artery (arteria carotis communis). After removing the skin from the cadaver, a paravertebral
128 incision was made, thereby releasing the TLF from the spine. Then the fascia was released by
129 blunt dissection from the back muscle up to the latissimus dorsi muscle, tensor fascia late
130 muscle and external oblique abdominis muscle. The collected TLF was immersed in a transport
131 solution (Hanks balanced salt solution) and transported to the laboratory at 4 °C. The chilled
132 fascia was removed from the test tube after 16 hours at 4 °C and moved along with the transport
133 solution to the sterilized Petri dish to prevent the tissue from drying out. Subsequently, the right
134 or left part of the fascia was taken out and spread on a glass plate, see Fig. 1. After measuring,
135 a sample of approximately 60×20 mm the test sample was cut out with dissecting scissors. The
136 prepared sample was attached to the tribometer.

137

138

139 Fig. 1 A summary diagram of the methods used for rabbit fascia in the present study. Created with
140 Biorender.com

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142 Fascia for electron microscopy scanning was washed with ultrapure water (Type II according
143 to ISO 3696, prepared on an Elix 5 UV Water Purification System (Merck, Germany)). Then,
144 the specimen was freeze-dried on an Epsilon 2-10D machine (Martin Christ, Osterode am
145 Hartz, Germany). A scanning electron microscope, MIRA3 (TESCAN, Czech Republic), was
146 used to study the morphology of the dried fascia sample. Images were taken in secondary
147 electron emission mode; the scan mode was DEPTH, the beam density was 10, and the high
148 voltage was 10 kV. The working distance was set to 15 mm. The surface of the sample was
149 coated with a 15 nm thin layer of Au using an EM ACE 600 (Leica Microsystems, Wetzlar,
150 Germany).

151

152 2.4 Pharmacokinetic study

153 The study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Ministry of Education, Youth and
154 Sports (approval No. MSMT-2036/2022-3).

155

156 For this study, 48 healthy, sexually mature New Zealand white male rabbits (weighing 2.7–3.5
157 kg) obtained from a certified laboratory animal breeder and supplier VELAZ, Ltd. (Prague,
158 Czech Republic) were used. The rabbits were acclimated for a period of two weeks before the
159 experiment began. The animals were housed individually in clean stainless-steel cages under
160 standardized environmental conditions (12-hour light/dark cycle, temperature 17-21 °C, air
161 humidity 30-70 %). The rabbits had access *ad libitum* to the standard diet for rabbits (VELAZ
162 Ltd., Prague, Czech Republic) and drinking water. The rabbits were randomly allocated into 8
163 groups, with 6 rabbits per group. The groups differed in the intrafascial injected solution (HA-
164 RED/¹³C-labelled 316 kDa HA) and in the euthanasia time after the solution administration
165 (1/3/7/30 days). The rabbits were first sedated by subcutaneous administration of medetomidine
166 (0.3 mg/kg; Domitor inj., Orion Corporation, Espoo, Finland) and then induced into general
167 anaesthesia by intramuscular administration of ketamine (25 mg/kg; Narkamon inj., Bioveta,
168 Ivanovice na Hane, Czech Republic). Subsequently, the rabbits were shaved on their backs
169 (approximately 4x4 cm in the application sites of the thoracolumbar spine area), and using a
170 25G needle under ultrasound guidance (Lumify, Philips, Netherlands), they were injected with
171 a 1% solution of ¹³C-labelled 316 kDa HA or a 1% solution of HA-RED (according to their
172 experimental group) in the amount of 0.7 ml on each side between the superficial and deep
173 layers of the thoracolumbar fascia at the level of the L2-L3 intervertebral junction, 50 mm
174 lateral to the spine (left and right). The application sites were then gently massaged manually
175 to evenly spread the injected solution between the fascial layers throughout the entire extent of
176 the fascia. At 1, 3, 7, or 30 days after the intrafascial administration of HA-RED or ¹³C-labelled
177 316 kDa HA solution, depending on the experimental group, the animals were sedated by
178 subcutaneous administration of medetomidine (0.3 mg/kg; Domitor inj., Orion Corporation,
179 Espoo, Finland) and then induced into general anaesthesia by intramuscular administration of

180 ketamine (25 mg/kg; Narkamon inj., Bioveta, Ivanovice na Hane, Czech Republic). A non-
181 coagulated blood sample (1 ml) was then collected from the central ear artery (arteria auricularis
182 centralis), centrifuged, and the plasma was separated. Subsequently, the animals were stunned
183 with a captive bolt gun and then exsanguinated by transecting the carotid artery (arteria carotis
184 communis). Then, after removing the skin from the rabbit cadavers, the TLF tissue samples
185 were obtained as two separate samples: a partial-thickness fascia (without the epimysial layer)
186 by separation from the spine through a paravertebral incision and releasing by blunt dissection
187 from the back muscles, and the corresponding epimysial layer with muscle tissue underneath.
188 Both types of samples were weighed separately, frozen individually at -20°C, and transported
189 to the laboratory for quantification of administered ¹³C-labelled 316 kDa HA and HA-RED in
190 the fascia and muscle by LC-MS.

191

192 **2.5 Determination of isotopically labelled HA and HA-RED in rabbit fascia and muscle**

193 For quantification of HA derivatives modified LC-MS method based on quantification of HA
194 disaccharides after enzymatic hydrolysis was employed [18] (S.Fig. 2). Briefly, weighted
195 samples of fascia and muscle were diluted with buffer (100 mM PBS with 10 mM EDTA, pH
196 7.4) and homogenized with Precellys Evolution homogenizer (Bertin Technologies, France).
197 To 100µl aliquot, internal standard of fully isotopically labelled 8x¹³C-HA (lower conc.) was
198 added and samples were incubated for 3 h at 45 °C with 40 µl of 1% Actinase E solution (Merck,
199 Germany) in HEPES buffer (pH 8). Afterwards, 1 µl of solution of hyaluronan lyase from
200 *Streptococcus pneumoniae* (Contipro a.s., Czech Republic) was added and samples were
201 incubated for 30 min at 37 °C. Finally, 400 µl of acetonitrile (LC-MS grade, VWR, USA) was
202 added, the samples were centrifuged (30 s, 10000 rpm) and supernatants were analysed by LC-
203 MS. A Vanquish Horizon chromatography system and a TQS Altis plus triple quadrupole mass
204 spectrometer (both Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) were used for analysis. 2 µl of sample were

205 injected onto an Acquity BEH HILIC Amide (2.1x100 mm) analytical column (Waters, UK)
206 tempered at 60 °C. The mobile phases consisted of 0.1% formic acid (v/v) (LC-MS grade,
207 Merck, Germany) and acetonitrile (LC-MS grade, VWR, USA). The gradient of acetonitrile
208 was as follows: 0-0.5 min 90%, 0.5-5 min 90-74%, 5-7 min 74-40%, 7-7.5 min 40-90%, 7.5-9
209 min 90%. The electrospray settings for the analysis were as follows: (capillary voltage -4000
210 V, Sheath gas 50, Aux gas 10, Sweep gas 0.5, ion transfer tube temp. 275 °C, vaporizer temp.
211 350 °C). MRM transitions of unsaturated disaccharides for $1x^{13}C$ -316kDa HA (lower conc.)
212 and fully labelled HA together with unsaturated tetrasaccharide of HA-RED were detected
213 during the analysis.

214

215 **2.6 Preparation of tribological samples from synthetic fascia**

216 The 1 mm synthetic substitute fascia consisted of multiple fiber planes was purchased from
217 SynDaver™ (Fibrous fascia, SKU: 141620) designed primarily for medical device design
218 testing and for medical professionals to practice surgery. Pre-preparation and storage of
219 synthetic fascia were performed according to manufacturer's instructions. The procedure for
220 cutting, sizing, and mounting the specimens further coincides with the preparation of
221 tribological samples from rabbit fascia.

222

223 **2.4 Statistical methods**

224 Results were presented as mean from 3 measurements \pm SD (standard deviation) unless
225 otherwise stated. Statistical criteria were verified by one-way or two-way ANOVA followed by
226 Tukey's or Bonferroni's multiple comparisons tests, with individual variances computed for
227 each comparison. For all tests, $*P < 0.05$, $**P < 0.01$, $***P < 0.001$, and $****P < 0.0001$ were
228 considered to be significant.

229

230 **3. Results**

231 **3.1 Testing of preload effect of fascia on friction**

232 In tribological testing, the material in the experimental setup is preloaded to simulate the
233 conditions experienced during muscle movement. Since stress levels can significantly impact
234 friction results, this study begins by parametrically analysing the effect of material preload on
235 friction, utilizing jaw prestressing. Subsequent friction experiments were conducted five times
236 using the 316kDa HA lubricant, chosen due to its medium molecular weight and widespread
237 use among the lubricants in this study. Fig. 2 illustrates that the bias level's effect on friction
238 had almost no effect for rabbit fascia when the fascia is prestressed. Statistical analysis revealed
239 the following significance levels: $P = 0.0427$ for the difference between weak and middle bias
240 levels, $P = 0.0542$ for the difference between weak and strong, and $P = 0.9752$ for the difference
241 between middle and strong for synthetic fascia. However, the influence of fascia prestressing
242 emerges as a slightly more significant factor in synthetic fascia. In instances where the fascia is
243 moderately or not prestressed, friction levels are lower compared to instances where the fascia
244 is strongly prestressed. The coefficient of friction (COF) increased from 0.0517 (SD = 0.0076)
245 or 0.04931 (SD = 0.0016) to 0.6275 (SD = 0.0023). Importantly, the bias level ceases to affect
246 friction in cases of strong prestress levels. For rabbit fascia, the significance levels were $P =$
247 0.8523 between weak and middle, $P = 0.2301$ between weak and strong, and $P = 0.0002$
248 between middle and strong bias levels. Considering the results from the parametric study, the

249 tribological tests in the following parts of the study were performed on a middle prestressed
 250 fascia.
 251

252
 253 Fig. 2 Level and friction influence of material prestressing of rabbit and synthetic fascia in experimental
 254 apparatus. The bias level represented level of material prestress from weak to strong

255
 256 **3.2 Short-term and long-term testing of fascia friction**

257 The friction experiments were conducted in two distinct stages. Initially, short-term tribological
 258 tests were conducted for 300 s. The results in Fig. 3 were analyzed to determine which lubricant
 259 most effectively reduces the friction of the fascia and its layers. This information is valuable in
 260 identifying suitable properties for viscosupplements for treating non-specific LBP. Statistical
 261 performance between the different lubricants is listed in S.Tab. 1. 101kDa HA and 316kDa HA
 262 (lower conc.) exhibited the lowest COF for both materials. However, 316kDa HA and HA-RED
 263 also demonstrated low friction with no significant difference observed for both *ex vivo* rabbit
 264 and synthetic fascia. Conversely, HA-C12 displayed the highest friction and standard deviation
 265 (SD) for synthetic fascia but the lowest for rabbit fascia. Lastly, 610kDa HA exhibited the
 266 highest friction, nearly double that of 101kDa HA and 316kDa HA (lower conc.), for both
 267 materials. The results of the short-term tests indicate that HA-RED has the same efficacy on

268 fascia friction as native HA with the same concentration and molecular weight. However, the
 269 interchangeability of HA-C12 with native HA remains debatable. Among the native HAs,
 270 101kDa HA and 316kDa HA (lower conc.) are the most effective candidates for successfully
 271 reducing friction in fascia and its layers.
 272

273
 274 Fig. 3 COF comparison of HA-based lubricants on rabbit and synthetic models. Differences between native HA
 275 lubricants and derivatives tested on synthetics fascia were *P < 0.05, shown in S.Tab 1. Black bar is labelled in
 276 terms of the plot name

277
 278 The second phase aimed to confirm the suitability of the lubricant for fascia lubrication based
 279 on long-term effects. Long-term tribological tests were conducted for 3000 s with other

280 experimental conditions maintained. The results were presented for each material in Fig. 4,
281 illustrating the evolution of friction over time for rabbit fascia and synthetic fascia, respectively.
282 These graphs are depicted as curves because the behavior of the lubricant in contact over time
283 is deemed more important than the final or average friction value. An overview of the graph
284 indicates that synthetic fascia exhibited a more consistent behavior throughout the long-term
285 test compared to other specimens, with fewer abrupt transitions and instabilities in the friction
286 curves. However, HA-C12 lubrication notably deteriorated the performance of synthetic fascia,
287 rendering it unsuitable for effective tribological testing with this lubricant. Conversely, the
288 performance of rabbit fascia remained relatively steady across most scenarios, showing no
289 significant deterioration in either case. Nonetheless, when paired with 610kDa HA lubricant,
290 slight fluctuations in performance were observed, with friction levels gradually increasing over
291 time. A similar but more nuanced trend was observed with 316kDa HA (lower conc.)
292 lubrication of rabbit fascia. Regarding HA-RED lubrication, one friction curve of rabbit fascia
293 exhibited instability and a slight upward trend over time. The results of the long-term assays
294 are consistent with the results of the short-term assays, confirming that HA-RED can replace
295 native HA with the same properties if it demonstrates longer stability *in vivo*. While HA-C12
296 exhibits low friction on biological fascia, its performance on synthetic fascia raises questions
297 about its long-term lubricating effects. Therefore, the benefits of HA-C12 compared with HA-
298 RED need to be carefully evaluated. Native HAs generally demonstrated good stability over
299 time. However, lower *MW* is associated with greater temporal stability, and lower
300 concentrations result in reduced friction. Therefore, the best native candidate for reducing
301 friction in the fascia and its layers is 316kDa HA (lower conc.).

302

Rabbit fascia
 Synthetic fascia

Fig. 4 Development of friction in time of 3000 (s) for rabbit and synthetic fascia.

303

304

305

306 **3.3 Pharmacokinetics of 316kDa HA (lower conc.) and HA-RED after application to the**

307 **fascia**

308 Based on the tribological results, 316kDa HA (lower conc.) and HA-RED were singled out as
 309 the candidates for the development of viscosupplementation for the treatment of non-specific
 310 LBP. To determine the pharmacokinetics of both materials and biodegradability of HA-RED,
 311 ¹³C-labelled HA and HA-RED were administered to live rabbits via intrafascial injection and
 312 number of administered materials were quantified in fascia and muscle by LC-MS.

313

314 Although a relatively large amount of 316kDa HA (lower conc.) is injected into the fascia (14
 315 mg corresponds to a dose of 5 mg/kg), after 3 days the amount of exogenous HA present in the
 316 fascia is very small (<2%) relative to the amount of endogenous HA in the tissue (see Fig. 5).
 317 The amount of endogenous HA in fascia was determined to be $412 \pm 73 \mu\text{g/g}$ and in muscle
 318 $12.8 \pm 1.9 \mu\text{g/g}$. Thus, the ratio of the concentration of ¹³C-HA in the fascia to that of
 319 endogenous HA decreased during 1, 3, 7 and 30 days as follows: 25.3%, 1.7%, 0.1%, 0.0%,
 320 respectively. In muscle, the ratio is then 14.4%, 0.3%, and 0.1% at 3 days, 7 days, and 30 days,
 321 respectively. The rate of elimination of applied ¹³C-HA from the fascia is thus relatively rapid.
 322 The elimination half-life in fascia and muscle was determined to be 20.1 h and 15.7 h,
 323 respectively. The concentration of ¹³C-HA was also determined in plasma and was determined
 324 to be below the detection limit of <100 ng/ml.

325

326

327 Fig. 5 Pharmacokinetics of ¹³C-316kDa HA (lower conc.) after injection into the fascia expressed as (A) the
 328 concentration of ¹³C-316kDa HA (lower conc.) per 1 g of tissue and (B) the amount of ¹³C-316kDa HA (lower
 329 conc.) in the tissue expressed as a proportion of the total amount injected

330 Quantification of HA-RED in fascial and muscle tissue by LC-MS was problematic since the
331 main unique product of enzymatic degradation unsaturated disaccharide of HA-RED lacks
332 ionizable carboxyl group and was undetectable by LC-MS (S.Fig. 2). Therefore, unsaturated
333 tetrasaccharide, the site product of enzymatic depolymerization, was used detection. However,
334 low abundance of tetrasaccharide and interferents present in the fascia and muscle specimens
335 that prevented accurate quantification of HA-RED thus its abundance in fascia and muscle was
336 evaluated at least semiquantitatively. The HA-RED signal was detected at 1, 3 and 7 days after
337 administration. As in the case of ^{13}C -HA, only trace amounts were present in the samples at 30
338 days after administration. The elimination half-life in fascia was around 108 h. The rate of
339 elimination could not be accurately evaluated, but the signal at 7 days was still significant, and
340 the elimination half-life in fascia was around 108 h suggesting that the HA-RED is
341 biodegradable material with slightly slower elimination rate than native HA.

342

343 **4. Discussion**

344 In this study, we examined six HA-based lubricants using *ex vivo* and synthetic fascia to identify
345 optimal HA properties that minimize friction within the fascia and its layers. HA plays a crucial
346 role in facilitating smooth movement within the fascia. Pathological conditions cause HA to
347 thicken, leading to tissue adhesion. In a previous study [14], we proposed a promising treatment
348 involving native HA intrafascial injections to reduce tissue friction and alleviate pain. Effective
349 agents must possess specific properties for optimal functionality. Therefore, our experiments
350 focused on understanding how the *MW*, chemical modification and concentration of HA
351 influence friction in fascia and its layers. The most promising HA derivative HA-RED from
352 tribological experiments was also tested for biodegradability using rabbits to ensure its safety
353 use for intrafascial injections.

354

355 **4.1 Influence of preload of fascia on friction**

356 The study begins by examining how stretching materials affect fascia friction. This
357 investigation is motivated by several factors. Firstly, during testing, the material is held in place
358 and slightly prestressed to mimic the natural tension fascia experiences. Fascia, which separates
359 muscles or fat, naturally undergoes stress with every movement due to muscle contractions or
360 external forces [19]. Structurally, fascia consists of three sublayers of connective tissue with
361 different densities and orientations [20; 21]. Studies have shown that within each sublayer,
362 collagen fibers run parallel, but the fibers in adjacent layers are oriented at angles of about 70-
363 80 degrees to each other [20]. Research on rabbit dorsal fascia demonstrated a similar structure
364 to human TLF, with collagen fibers and loose connective tissue [14]. Notably, only the
365 superficial sublayer is richly innervated and contains few elastic fibers [21]. Collagen fibers,
366 visible in the study's images (see Fig. 6), provide resistance to tension and stretching, common
367 in various fascial tissues like ligaments, tendons, sheaths, muscular fascia, and deeper fascial
368 sublayers [22]. The collagen and three-layer structure of the fascia, designed to allow fiber
369 sliding within each layer [23; 24], likely explains why preloading did not affect the friction of
370 HA within the rabbit fascia. In contrast, synthetic fascia showed higher friction under heavier
371 preload. The synthetic material, consisting of three sublayers with hydrophilic polymer on the
372 top and bottom and fibers in the middle, might have experienced top-layer wear under increased
373 stress.

Fig. 6 Close-ups of the fascia specimens used, captured using the SEM method

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These thinner layers are more prone to damage from stretching and tangential forces during friction tests, leading to rougher fiber surfaces (Fig. 7). When the top fiber surface contacts the material, additional contact area is observed with more compliant elastomers, indicating hysteretic friction [25]. Hysteretic friction likely increases with higher surface roughness, leading to a higher COF [26]. However, this hypothesis requires further analysis. Future viscosupplements should maintain low friction levels without being compromised by stress and wear in pathological conditions. Additionally, future experiments should note that there is no significant difference in friction between lightly and moderately prestressed material, so materials will not be overstressed in further tests.

Fig. 7 Synthetic fascia layers behavior under the preloading, normal load and sliding conditions

4.2 Advantage of HA derivatization in solution and its influence on friction

A notable drawback of using HA in medicine is its relatively rapid degradation in the human body, which limits its duration of action. To prolong the stay at the application site, HA can be chemically modified [27]. However, a crucial characteristic of natural HA is its mucoadhesiveness and biocompatibility needs to be preserved. [28]. . In this study, both native HA (610kDa, 316kDa and 101kDa HA) and two HA derivatives (HA-RED and HA-C12) were tested. HA-RED is HA with carboxyl groups partly reduced to primary alcohols, which provides higher thermal stability and resistance to enzymatic degradation [16]. The chemically modified HA has not been tested previously for treatment of LBP, however they have been extensively studied to restore lubrication of joints in OA [29] and some of them are clinically used (e.g. Hylan G-F 20). Comparing the results of native HA and HA-RED with similar MW (316 vs. 275 kDa), we observe that the chemical derivatization had no significant impact on fascia friction. Despite a minor decrease in viscosity, the influential factors remained *MW* and concentration parameters. HA-C12 is an amphiphilic form of HA known for its resistance to enzymatic degradation and ability to interact by ionic interactions as well as by hydrophobic interactions [30]. Compared to native HA, this derivative exhibits significantly more pronounced shear-thinning behavior [31]. Previously, it has also been studied for use in eye

406 drops to treat dry eyes [32]. In these studies, HA-C12 showed extremely low friction and
407 effectively prevented surface eye cells from drying out, surpassing the effectiveness of regular
408 HA. However, the effect of HA-C12 derivation on fascia friction alone cannot be assessed as
409 the lubricant has a different concentration than the others used. The effect of the lubricant itself
410 on friction will be discussed in the next chapter.

411

412 **4.3 Selection of appropriate properties of HA-based solution as a viscosupplement of TLF** 413 **fascia based on friction results**

414 In this study, the viscosity of HA solutions increased with increasing *MW* and concentration, as
415 shown in Tab 1. The reason for this increase is
416 straightforward: the viscosity of a polymer solution depends on the proportion of the solution's
417 volume taken up by the polymer chains. This proportion can be described by the concentration
418 of the polymer multiplied by its specific volume [6]. In simpler terms, viscosity is influenced
419 by the length and number of polymer chains in the solution, as well as the size of the molecules
420 themselves. As *MW* and concentration rise, the polymer chains become more tightly packed,
421 making it harder for them to move freely within the solution. Consequently, when minimal
422 sliding and pressure are applied, friction between the molecules increases. This conclusion is
423 supported by the findings of the short-term friction experiments, as seen in Fig. 3.

424

425 The tribological experiments also supported the statement that a high-viscosity solution may
426 not be ideal for promoting fascial glide [10; 11; 12]. These solutions (610kDa HA, 316kDa HA,
427 and HA-RED) exhibited higher friction coefficients. In contrast,
428 Fig. 3 shows a noticeable decrease in friction of native HA (101kDa HA and 316kDa HA (lower
429 conc.)) with decreasing *MW* and concentration for both fascial models. Surprisingly, this is the
430 opposite of what happens in an osteoarthritic joint [33; 34] or the eye and eyelid [13]. The most

431 interesting comparison is with HA-C12, which may explain how HA behaves toward fascia.
432 For rabbit fascia, a solution with a concentration of 3 mg/ml and a low *MW* of 318 kDa achieved
433 super-low friction. However, the friction of the synthetic fascia was almost five times higher.
434 This demonstrates that HA has limited capacity to adhere to both hydrophilic and hydrophobic
435 artificial surfaces [35]. In contrast, for tissue, collagen fibers on cartilage deform under
436 boundary lubrication [36], reducing gaps laterally while maintaining size normally. This
437 deformation allows collagen fibers to mechanically entrap HA molecules. While the forces
438 binding the molecules to the fibers are not strong enough to create a complete lubricating layer
439 [37], unlike phospholipids and HA [38; 39; 40], the HA trapped in this manner can still serve
440 as a boundary layer, preventing cartilage damage. HA-C12 has a low concentration and
441 viscosity, forming a weaker lubricating film. Therefore, the synergy between collagen fibers
442 and HA helps protect fascia against wear and damage. Synthetic fascia, lacking collagen, does
443 not form this layer, leading to rapid wear. Even a concentration as small as 3 mg/ml is a suitable
444 option for viscosupplementation of fascia.

445
446 The HA-collagen synergy likely manifested in other cases as well. For 610kDa HA, the
447 longitudinal test curves for synthetic fascia show a smooth progression throughout the
448 experiment, as seen in Fig. 4. The *MW* and concentration of 610kDa HA and the likely low
449 roughness of the synthetic fascia contributed to forming a minimally weak lubricating film,
450 protecting the fascia from damage. For rabbit fascia, regular waves can be seen in the progress.
451 This may be explained by the viscoelastic properties of HA at higher *MWs*, as shown by [41],
452 combined with how collagen entraps HA between its fibers [36]. The friction gradually
453 increases until it reaches its peak and then decreases gradually. This suggests that 610kDa HA,
454 due to its large macromolecular clusters [6], does not reach deep between the collagen fibers
455 but attaches mechanically to their surface, causing an increase in friction. Due to the viscoelastic

456 properties of HA and the shear frictional bias, the chains tear into smaller ones, as described in
457 [6; 42; 43], again protecting the fascia from damage.

458

459 **4.4 HA Degradation in Living Organisms and Viscosupplement Confrontation**

460 The suitability of native versus reduced HA for treating non-specific LBP was further assessed
461 through pharmacokinetics. The viscosupplement is designed to dilute endogenous HA, which
462 becomes highly viscous due to pathological changes in fascial tissue [10; 11]. Based on friction
463 results, 316kDa HA (lower conc.) and HA-RED (275 kDa) were selected for comparison.
464 However, previous research has shown that HA solutions degrade more slowly *in vivo* with
465 higher *MW* compared to lower *MW* [17]. Consequently, 101kDa HA, despite having the same
466 COF but a lower *MW*, was not chosen for *in vivo* experiments. The turnover rate of endogenous
467 HA in the body is relatively rapid, with a half-life of 2-5 minutes in the bloodstream [44] and a
468 few days in tissues [45]. If low dose of exogenous are used ($\sim\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$) its elimination is fast and
469 similar to elimination of endogenous HA, however, if HA is dosed at relatively high doses in
470 the range of mg kg^{-1} HA elimination follows saturable kinetics, where the elimination half-life
471 can reach several hours HA. HA is eliminated from the body through local cleavage reactions
472 and systemic elimination via the liver, lymphatics, and kidneys. At the cellular level, HA
473 undergoes non-specific degradation by free radicals or specific depolymerization by various
474 enzymes [17].

475

476 HA administered via intrafascial injection at dose 5 mg/kg exhibited elimination half-life of
477 which is expected for this *MW* (same citation). It is appealing to use HA with higher *MW* to
478 prolong its stay in fascia and enhance the effectiveness of the viscosupplement. However,
479 formulations with excessively high *MW* have been reported to cause local harm [46] and its
480 application is problematic due to the high viscosity of solutions of high-*MW* HA [14]. The

481 chemical derivatization of HA of seems as more promising approach to prolong the stay of
482 viscosupplementation at application site, as the viscosity is unaltered and resistance to
483 enzymatic degradation is enhanced. The pharmacokinetics of HA-RED showed excellent
484 biocompatibility and biodegradability since after 30 days all HA-RED was eliminated similarly
485 as native HA as native HA of similar *MW*. HA-RED exhibited longer elimination half-life
486 (108 h) than native HA (20.1 h). Although, chemical modification of HA ensures higher *in vivo*
487 stability, the elimination of viscosupplementation remains relatively fast. Despite this,
488 viscosupplementation based on HA can be effective, as evidenced in the case of
489 viscosupplementation for OA.

490

491 Viscosupplementation with HA is a well-established treatment for OA of the joints, where the
492 administered HA is absorbed within days [47]. However, the clinical efficacy of intra-articular
493 HA injections for managing knee OA pain reaches its maximum around 6-8 weeks after
494 administration, with uncertain benefits at 6 months [48]. This extended relief may be attributed
495 to HA's ability to initiate secondary processes despite its rapid degradation. HA can reduce
496 nerve impulses and sensitivity linked to OA pain [49]. In experimental OA models, HA has
497 shown protective effects on cartilage, likely mediated by its molecular and cellular interactions
498 observed *in vitro*. Exogenous HA stimulates HA and proteoglycan synthesis in chondrocytes,
499 reduces the production and activity of proinflammatory mediators and matrix
500 metalloproteinases, and modulates immune cell behavior. Furthermore, dermal HA fillers are
501 known to enhance fibroblast production, and alleviating inflammatory skin conditions [50].
502 Fasciocytes [51], which produce HA in the fascia, are fibroblast-like cells contributing to these
503 effects. HA has documented wound healing properties [52] and it is crucial in regulating cell
504 behavior, promoting cell proliferation within an HA-rich extracellular matrix [53]. These

505 physiological effects collectively contribute to the mechanisms through which HA exert its
506 clinical benefits in the viscosupplement treatment even for fascia tissue and non-specific LBP.

507

508 **5. Conclusion**

509 In this study, HA-based lubricants were tribologically tested to optimize solution's properties
510 leading to low friction of fascia tissue. The aim of this study was to assess whether the HA
511 derivative could substitute the native HA form, preserving its superior frictional properties, with
512 an assumed slower degradation *in vivo*. Tribological tests were supplemented by
513 pharmacokinetics of the two most promising lubricants a living rabbit model, contributing to
514 the development of advanced therapeutic solutions. To summarize the main conclusions and
515 contributions of the study:

516 1. **Tribological model - Optimization of fascia prestressing:** The medium rabbit and
517 synthetic fascia prestress ensures that the final friction results will be influenced by the
518 effect of the lubricant without being affected by the degree of fascia tension. Artificial
519 fascia is good model for tribological testing, as most of tested HA solutions exhibited
520 same friction coefficients.

521 2. **Lubricants:** 316 kDa HA and HA-RED were identified as having the best and most stable
522 tribological properties for fascia lubricants, driven by their *MW* and concentration.

523 3. **Pharmacokinetics of intrafascial HA-based viscosupplementation:** Chemically
524 modified HA (HA-RED) is eliminated within 30 days as well as native HA, however, it
525 exhibits a longer residence time compared to native HA.

526 The effectiveness of HA viscosupplementation in treating non-specific LBP is influenced not
527 only by its tribological properties and residence time at the application site but also by its
528 regulatory functions. This multifaceted impact of HA is supported by its successful use in
529 viscosupplementation for OA.

530

531 **Ethical approval**

532 The procedure for obtaining the TLF was approved by the Ethics Committee of the MINISTRY
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534

535

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545

546 **Declaration of interests**

547 The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal
548 relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

549

550 **Data Availability**

551 Experimental data for *Hyaluronic Acid-Based Lubricants Tribology for Alleviating Non-*
552 *Specific Lower Back Pain* available at resource DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11239441.

553

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555

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561 S.Fig. 1 Structures of native HA and its derivatives: reduced HA (HA-RED) and lauroyl-modified HA (HA-C12)

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563 S.Fig. 2 Enzymatic depolymerization of fully labelled native HA (14x¹³C-HA), reduced-HA (HA) and 2x¹³C-
 564 labelled native HA (2x¹³C-HA) into unsaturated oligosaccharides. Fragmentations of deprotonated unsaturated
 565 oligosaccharides were measured in negative ion mode. Unsaturated disacchide of HA-RED lacks of ionizable
 566 carboxyl group and was undetectable in LC-MS, therefore unsaturated tetrasaccharide, the site product of
 567 enzymatic degradation was used for quantification

S.Fig. 3 COF comparison of HA-based lubricants on rabbit and synthetic models

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571 To demonstrate how the synthetic fascia compares to real rabbit tissue in friction and lubrication
 572 studies. Six HA-based lubricants with different formulations were used, and the friction results,
 573 along with further statistical significance of the different models shown in S.Fig. 4, illustrate
 574 how each material performed with each lubricant. For 316kDa HA, 101kDa HA, and HA-RED,
 575 the friction results indicated complete interchangeability and no significant difference in COF
 576 (ns; $P > 0.9999$). A slight difference was observed for 610kDa HA (**; $P = 0.0037$) and 316kDa
 577 HA (lower conc.) (**; $P = 0.0064$), while HA-C12 (****; $P < 0.0001$) showed the most
 578 significant differences. As can be seen, synthetic fascia has become an interchangeable model
 579 of rabbit fascia.

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S.Tab. 1 Significance of friction results between individual lubricants

Designation	<i>Ex vivo</i> rabbit fascia	Synthetic fascia
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	Significance	Adjusted P value	Significance	Adjusted P value
610kDa HA vs. 316kDa HA	***	0.0009	**	0.0013
610kDa HA vs. 101kDa HA	***	0.0002	****	<0.0001
610kDa HA vs. 316kDa HA (lower conc.)	***	0.0007	****	<0.0001
610kDa HA vs. HA-RED	****	<0.0001	*	0.0164
610kDa HA vs. HA-C12	***	0.0003	*	0.0273
316kDa HA vs. 101kDa HA	****	<0.0001	****	<0.0001
316kDa HA vs. 316kDa HA (lower conc.)	*	0.0117	***	0.0007
316kDa HA vs. HA-RED	ns	0.2122	ns	0.3113
316kDa HA vs. HA-C12	*	0.0239	*	0.0168
101kDa HA vs. 316kDa HA (lower conc.)	ns	0.9949	*	0.0172
101kDa HA vs. HA-RED	*	0.0422	*	0.0116
101kDa HA vs. HA-C12	ns	0.3129	*	0.0121
316kDa HA (lower conc.) vs. HA-RED	ns	0.0674	*	0.0134
316kDa HA (lower conc.) vs. HA-C12	ns	0.4369	*	0.0125
HA-RED vs. HA-C12	**	0.0080	*	0.0125

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